

ARCHITECTURAL AND DESIGN DESIGN OF AGGLOMERATION COMMERCIAL COMPLEXES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *It is necessary to plan the shopping center on the basis of a strict project, taking into account the implementation of various functional and technological processes in the proposed retail and service complexes. Because of the large size of the center, the prospect of a long, monotonous-looking gallery has become so boring that it is natural to be unable to attract the attention of visitors.*

Key words: *Project, function, technology, trade and consumer services, complex*

The government of Uzbekistan has included in the priority directions development of urban territories and restoration of residential, public and industrial buildings, strengthening the material and technical base of the production of new building materials and structures.

Despite the numerous researchers conducted in our country, it is observed that in all cities of the Republic, including Jizzakh, Karshi and Urgench, many commercial and domestic service complexes and large shopping centers, as well as their project proposals, are often placed without adaptation to dry-hot climatic conditions and are not created favorable conditions for the customers.

As a result of the fact that customers lose a lot of time to realize their desires and use of services, as well as the lack of organization of recreation zones for

young children and the elderly, suitable conditions for local and foreign tourists, the useful working coefficient and efficiency of market and commercial complexes are becoming low. Taking into account the above mentioned shortcomings and mistakes, the development, improvement and creation of projects of modern commercial and household service complexes with a new type of architectural-planning solution for regional centers of Uzbekistan at the level of agglomeration on the basis of urban planning principles is an important issue in actual and practical terms [7].

Taking into account the implementation of various functional and technological processes in the shopping and consumer service complexes under the project, planning of the center on the basis of a solid project (when the area is more than 5000 m²) is required. Because, since the center area is large, the prospect of a long monotonous-looking gallery has become a natural phenomenon that today evokes a feeling of boredom and does not attract the attention of visitors.

The design of commercial and household service complexes should be carried out on the basis of the following criteria [8].

1. The south-facing sides of commercial and household service complexes can overheat. Therefore, the dimensions of the windows should be small, darkened windows should be designed on the walls facing East and West.

2. Since the trade-household service complex is based on the concept of "prices", it is necessary to pay special attention to the fact that the back walls of the trading hall look good and are illuminated, taking into account that the building is made up of curved lines and elements with a complex appearance.

3. Very wide corridors for shopping and household service complexes are not formed. Because, in addition to the fact that people lose themselves in this "free" movement and fall into confusion, the network of corridors can complicate the orientation of buyers and cause a violation of the direction of flow.

4. It is recommended that the halls of trade and household services complex should be designed on the basis of atrium and Galerie schemes, so that everyone is comfortable [1].

In order to attract the attention of customers, different planning magnets are placed every 100 meters. Taking into account the fact that it is convenient to go to every corner of the center building for people with limited mobility, as well as for mothers with young children, separate elevators intended for them are provided in the building, and it is recommended that they should be designed on the basis of the shortest distance from the exit door on the evacuation.

Design of commercial and household service complexes for Karshi, Jizzakh and Urgench cities - modern commercial and household service centers have been designed based on the main normative and sectoral documents (on the basis of building standards and rules, interagency building standards) and the results of scientific and practical research obtained from world practice.

5. It should be noted that "magnets" or "single shots" – together with shops located at strategic points and small specialized stores placed between them form universal Stores and food supermarkets. The center should have a comfortable car park (but vehicles are not allowed to enter the area), an attractive landscape plan, a restaurant with a high level of comfort, a sports center, cinemas, artistic sights and other additional attractions can be found [7].

For all this, it is also necessary to create favorable conditions for extended trading day trading. This will be the "coverage area", that is, the usual shopping center, which depends on the successful operation in regional agglomerations. With the development of "Natural Environmental Engineering, namely air conditioning, progressive artificial lighting, an indoor shopping center or indoor mall" appears [1].

6. At present, on the one hand, it is required to pay attention to the fact that the cities are badly developed and, on the other hand, to provide services to the growing urban population. Thus, the planned trade will appear classic collections of household service complexes.

7. The first attempts to rebuild urban centers in Uzbekistan were not successful enough. The cities of Karshi, Jizzakh and Urgench are being rebuilt, without taking into account the importance of shops and points of sale, since they are located on

both sides of a wide range of transport routes, the effectiveness of the use of existing parcels and the transport connection are not taken into account.

8. In the twentieth century, in many cities of the world, projects for the reconstruction of the Central Districts were carried out, many of which relentlessly reacted and broke down to the elements of the traditional city, replacing residential buildings and standard shops on the first floors with an economically viable solution [6].

9. In the plots and general location of the shopping center, an interesting and cozy atmosphere characteristic of the oldest market was lost due to the fact that pedestrians did not have good access.

An extremely important condition for the successful development of the shopping center is its location. For the placement of the shopping center, transport links with other population pinks of the regional center should be taken into account. Suitable geographic location for the construction site is determined by the economic aspects that characterize the area. The economic aspect is related to the fact that the core of agglomeration is adapted to trade and service. When considering two land plots that may be identical in all other respects, it is necessary to carefully consider their location and relevant economic data. To avoid the risk of setting up a trade center blindly, it is necessary to take into account the nature of the territory in which the Trade Center is located, regardless of whether there is always a selected place or there is still no relevant place [5].

If the territory has already been selected, then the work of the Economist should be aimed at studying the economic characteristics of the construction site within the framework of agglomeration. The results of his research should serve as the basis for deciding whether or not the chosen place is suitable for the construction and development of the shopping center. If the issue is resolved positively, on the basis of the information received, the size and structure of the shopping center should be determined [5].

When this research methodology is thoroughly and properly analyzed, it will generally help to determine the most suitable place for the construction of a

commercial center with the importance of agglomeration. However, it is also important to conduct a survey to describe the existing area or to create a new location of the shopping center, and the main research methods will be very similar [7].

The purpose of the economic analysis is to obtain detailed economic data so that it will be possible to determine the approximate size of retail sales acceptable for a particular place where the Trade Center is expected to be built. In any economic analysis, usually the following factors are studied: the income of the population, the purchasing power of the population, the convenience of approaching the rival shops, the future shopping center and other conditions. The main factor determining the location of the shopping center is the issue of the population. If the entire population of agglomeration uses the center of trade, then the economic efficiency will be higher [9].

To ensure the successful operation of the shopping center, its location must be coordinated with the components of agglomeration. Therefore, if we consider that in the future the center will be located, then this should be provided for in the preliminary planning. If at the beginning there were no such measures, then in some exceptional cases, provided that the land was additionally taken, it is still possible to expand the center.

However, the chances of such an expand being harmonious and very successful are greatly reduced. In some cases, the successful development of the centers can be achieved by the construction of additional buildings, which are not provided for in the initial project. Since there is no reserve space for such a construction, new buildings should be built in the place where they were first used for parking lots, and the effectiveness of this measure should be reduced. This somehow determines the initial success of the center [3].

In this regard, the turnover of not only new stores, but the whole center, often suffer. When planning the growth of the center, two main issues will be considered here: planning the development of the center and the development of the center in stages [3].

1. Plan to focus. In most cases, the whole center is built together in one row. This means that all the basic elements that make up the complete organism of the shopping center are being built. At the same time, the possibility of expanding individual stores, the construction of new stores or the implementation of both methods of centralization is created when the initial plan is drawn up, regardless of whether this opportunity will be used in the near or far future.

2. Plan the stages of development of the Center. In this case, at the first stage, only part of the final plan is completed. Only some basic elements of the final plan will be built. It is advisable to plan a hike when the shopping center is located in a place where there is always growth.

There are many necessary conditions for the planning of the center. One of the main conditions is the development of agglomeration relations and the proximity of the shopping center with transport nodes. It is important that the transport nodes have good connections with public transportation stops. The possible permeability capacity of the surrounding main roads should be at a level suitable for additional transport loads. The area should be large enough to store a reserve area for additional buildings, parking lots and traffic movements, or additional income should justify capital investments for the construction of a two- or multi-storey car park during the expansion of the center [3].

The most important thing is that when the designer plans to establish a center, he should be sure that the volume of commercial and household services can generate income for the increased sales potential. If there are regions suitable for trade, for example, for trade centers, then in the future there is a high probability of such competition. These cases must first be thoroughly considered and a decision to expand the center will be made [3].

Measures to further expand the center will require capital investments, which must be carried out at the time of initial construction. In this regard, the planning of the centralization will be considered acceptable in the near future when there will be such expansion opportunities. Nevertheless, the possibility of expanding the

center can be of great importance, if it is necessary to ensure the maintenance of a superior position of the center in the shopping zone.

For a group of additional shops with the necessary pedestrian corridors and empty spaces, the area should be part of the initial zone plan and thus should be maintained so that a significant gap should not appear in the first phase of the shopping center. In this case, planning should be carried out in such a way as to ensure complete regulation of these new buildings with a previously built Center [6].

In order to meet the demand for parking lots as a result of the outflow of commercial premises, space must also be stored in reserve. When determining the reserve area necessary for this purpose, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that it is located in relation to new or existing buildings of the shopping center, so as not to create excessively large distances between the parking lot and pedestrian areas.

After the completion of the initial construction, this reserve area should be landscaped accordingly, so as not to spoil the overall appearance of the shopping center. When designing and building auxiliary rooms, warehouses and distribution systems, it is necessary to take into account the measures to expand them in proportion to the increasing needs of agglomeration population.

Conclusion: it is necessary to rely on architectural and planned solutions of commercial and domestic service complexes and many factors affecting the formation, as well as the requirements for its placement in the structure of agglomeration, as well as recommended norms and practical work experience.

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